

Effect of Forensic Accounting Techniques on Fraud Detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State

By

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of forensic accounting techniques on fraud detection by professional accounting firms in Plateau State. A survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 6 accounting and auditing professional firms in Plateau State. Oral interview was used to ascertain the total number of staff from these firms totaling 203, whereby a sample size of 135 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. A total of 135 copies of questionnaire were administered on the selected respondents. However, 129 copies were retrieved. The study employed the use of structured questionnaire as method of data collection and the hypotheses were tested using multiple regression as method of data analysis. Findings shows that data mining technique had a positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State; reviewing financial statement technique had a negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State; analyzing accounting records techniques have positive and not significant effect on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State and Internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State. The study recommended Professional Accounting Firms and other private organizations should select data mining software that integrates with existing accounting systems; Professional accounting firms should maintain the services of forensic accountants to review their financial statements and transactions at the end of the period of transactions; Professional accounting firms should employ the services of forensic accountants to help them unveil fraudulent records from their financial books and Firms should determine critical internal controls for financial reporting.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting Techniques, Fraud Detection, Professional Accounting Firms

1. INTRODUCTION

Professional accounting firms have advanced at a rapid pace by the profound changes in the activities by accounting professionals (Supriadi et al., 2020). First of all, the capacity to automate various firms and business procedures have greatly expedited operations in companies across by industrial sectors, freeing accountants of regular debiting and crediting responsibilities (Maiti et al., 2021). Second, the financial statements produced by the accountants have been overshadowed by the many reports produced by management, analysts, mutual funds, and a host of other actors since the development of the Internet (Moll & Yigitbasioglu, 2019). Third, as a global economy becomes more demanding, accountants have to deal with foreign markets, their accounting standards, currencies, financial derivatives, spinoffs, divestitures, tracking stocks, and the numerous transactions that take place in the financial sector and professional firms (Boolakay et al., 2018). The professional accountant needed to acquire a whole new set of skills to cope with this changing environment (Napier & Stadler, 2020). Over the years, a growing number of concerning audit failures have prompted a paradigm shift in accounting (Byrnes et al., 2018). However, a new area of accounting called “forensic accounting” has emerged and is now in charge of looking for signs of material fabrication, error, and fraud (Kranacher & Riley, 2019). Forensic accounting technique is developed to detect fraud and combat the threat in reaction to some newly discovered fraudulent cases (Afriyie et al., 2023; Sahdan et al., 2021).

According to Tekavčič and Damijan (2021), it is difficult to estimate the level of fraud in the world because the impact of losses experienced can be shocking for the world economy, destroying hopes of prosperity and economic efficiency in the future. The global impact of fraudulent activity is challenging to estimate because fraudulent acts often receive little attention and are not reported. However, according to information revealed in the 2021 ACFE (Association of Certified Fraud Examiners) report, every year, a company loses 5% of its revenue due to fraudulent acts, and it is estimated that this loss reaches almost \$4 trillion globally (Mittal, Kaur, & Gupta, 2021). This condition proves that fraud is a challenge for today’s modern economy and can even occur widely and quickly because fraud occurs anywhere and anytime without being easily detected (Firmanza, Abidin & Ruswanda, 2022).

The use of contemporary forensic accounting methods in audits is thought to be appropriate in order to equip accounting professionals to handle the challenge of identifying clever fraud schemes that result from audits' inability to identify frauds in Nigeria. Applying investigative techniques, the forensic accountant makes it feasible to detect fraud. Regardless of whether they are ultimately employed in a trial, forensic accountants employ as many of these accounting methods as they can in order to identify fraud. These techniques include interviewing, invigilation, observation, vulnerability and internal control charts, net worth method, expenditure method, bank deposit method, cash transaction method, document examination, tracing, data mining technique, ratio analysis among others according to Oyedokun (2019). He further stated that forensic accounting techniques such as interviewing, computer assisted reviews such as data mining, and document review techniques are useful to detect fraud.

Fraud has been a precipitating element in the failure of enterprises and organizations, and despite numerous steps made to reduce the occurrence of fraud, it continues to rise by the day since fraudsters always find creative ways of committing fraud. This has become a hot topic in organizations and businesses. Nigeria's condition is so bad that the rate and amount of fraudulent operations were so high that the country ranked 146th out of 180 nations in the 2019 Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) with a 26%. In Nigeria, there have been some high-level corruption cases, such as the over 8.5 billion naira alleged no remittance of recovered funds by the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) leadership, the alleged diverted 1.9 billion naira Ebola fight fund, the \$20 billion NNPC case, the famous 'Arm Scam Deal' of \$2 billion in 2015, and the N5.5 billion Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), 2020,

contract scam involving Signora Concept Services LTD, among others, which occurred in Jos, Plateau State. For instance, Moruf Tunji Olukanmi, a staff of First Bank, Jos Plateau State on July 21st, 2021 was found to have been involved in for fraud involving over N900 million Point of Sale (POS) transactions. (Ugwu, 2021)

Forensic accounting techniques are not widely adopted in Plateau State, leading to a lack of effective fraud detection; professionals in Plateau State may not have the necessary training and expertise to apply forensic accounting techniques, and organizations in Plateau State may not have the necessary resources (technology, funding) to implement forensic accounting techniques and some of the practical gaps that this research would fill. In the methodological gap, there is limited collaboration between professionals, organizations, and law enforcement agencies in Plateau State, hindering the effective use of forensic accounting techniques. In addition, there is a need for more research on the effectiveness of forensic accounting techniques in Plateau State's context; hence, this research is narrowed to some selected professional accounting and auditing firms on the Plateau using survey design to fill the methodological gap and practical gap (Rahab & Ayad, 2019)

Furthermore, there is a need for a comprehensive legal framework that supports the use of forensic accounting techniques in fraud detection in Plateau State. The need for more research on the development of fraud theories and how they can be applied in Plateau State is a problem. However, the theoretical gap of this research can be filled with the anchor theory which is fraud management lifecycle theory. The theory explains the rudiments and expectancies of forensic accounting techniques in detecting fraud. Studies of Okoye, et al. (2019) were hinged on Fraud Triangle Theory.

The cases of frauds in organizations have made auditing and investigation ineffective in terms of detection of fraud by Professional accounting firms and business organisations in Plateau State. Due to the increase in the rate of financial fraud, the need to detect fraud is necessary in professional accounting firms, and is not a responsibility of a traditional auditor. Thus, a need for the services of forensic accountants whose primary responsibility is to detect fraud (Mbasiti, et al. 2021). As a result of poor confidence in the traditional audit profession, forensic accounting has become a growing field of accounting that helps in fraud detection, by using both accounting, auditing and investigation skills to arrive at a logical conclusion (Aduwo, 2016). Consequently, forensic accounting/auditing goes a step beyond the traditional role of auditors because it examines the nature of business transaction by checking for possibility of fraudulent activities through the use of Data Mining technique, reviewing financial statement, Analyzing Accounting Records technique and internal control charts technique which are believed to have an edge over the role of an auditor in fraud detection.

Without a doubt, a great deal of research has been conducted in this area. Studies like Okoye (2016), Olaoye and Adebayo (2019), Safiyanu, Safiyanu and Armaya'u (2019), Ojo-Agbodu et al. (2022), Afriyie et al. (2023), Gideon and Omolara (2024) have all shown how important forensic accounting is to the detection of fraud. However, none of these studies were able use the techniques of Data Mining, reviewing financial statement, Analyzing Accounting Records and internal control charts to detect fraud by accounting firms. This study attempts to bridge this gap by looking into these forensic accounting techniques in fraud detections by professional accounting firms in Plateau State, Nigeria. Although the study by Mbasiti, *et al.* (2021) used forensic accounting techniques of forensic accounting data analysis and forensic accounting technology as tools for preventing revenue leakages in federal universities, it failed to investigate the application of these techniques adopted for this study for fraud detection in professional accounting firms of Plateau State which is also a gap to be filled by this study. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of forensic accounting

techniques on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State to fill the geographical gap that other research couldn't in their work.

This study attempts to answer the following questions: to what extent does data mining technique affect fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State?, to what extent does reviewing financial statement technique affect fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State?, to what extent does analyzing accounting records technique affect fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State?, to what extent does internal control charts affect fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State?

The following research hypotheses shall be tested to conclude. They include; Data mining technique has no significant effect on fraud detection by Accounting Professional Firms in Plateau State, reviewing financial statement techniques has no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, analyzing accounting records techniques have no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, and internal control charts have no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State.

2.0 Literature review

2.1.1 Concept of Fraud

Fraud has been variously defined in different literatures. According to Kania, et al., (2023), fraud is an act of cheating by presenting false financial information to deceive or obtain unlawful financial gain, which is carried out intentionally; the losses experienced are usually in the form of money or assets that can be assessed.

Safiyanu, Safiyanu & Armaya'u (2019) describe fraud as a deliberate act of deception intended to gain an advantage. The immoral act of falsifying data and/or figures for personal gain is known as fraud. Furthermore, despite the fact that the intended benefits might not be immediate cash in hand, Olaoye and Adebayo (2019) argued that scammers' ultimate goal is to obtain an unfair financial edge.

Fraud, according to Udeh and Ugwu (2018), is the deliberate misrepresentation or fabrication of facts with the goal of gaining an advantage or hiding shady transactions so that users may eventually suffer losses as a result of relying on the information. According to Okoye (2016), fraud is the willful theft or exploitation of organizational resources with the intention of making money off of one's position. As a result, it is theft, burglary, or embezzlement of business assets.

Okpala & Enwefa (2017) define fraud as an intentional or purposeful misrepresentation that causes harm to another individual. It is intentional deception that results in harm to another individual, typically in the form of financial losses. The breadth and context of fraudulent schemes vary, particularly depending on the position of the criminals within an organization. Bribery, misappropriation, poor financial management, and budget padding are all prevalent in the public sector.

2.1.2 Concept of Fraud detection

Fraud Detection is the application of investigative skill to expose and uncover an intentional or deliberate act by an employee of the firm to divulge vital information in order to perpetrate fraudulent activities and financial crime. The goal of fraud detection is to identify any anomalies or deviations from the desired process flow. Criminality analysis requires the direct recognition of organizations genuine or possible criminality (Ojo-Agboodu, Abiola, & Ndubusi, 2022).

According to Gideon and Omolara (2024), detection is the process of seeing or recognizing something or someone as they are acting. Fraud detection is the practice of spotting fraud as soon as it has been committed. Methods for detecting fraud are always being developed to help crooks adjust their tactics. Since criminals may utilize this information to create more

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complex fraud strategies, it is not appropriate to discuss fraud methods and fraud detection in public. (Gideon & Omolara, 2024)

According to Ogutu and Ngahu (2016), forensic accounting approaches give accountants the tools they need to act as "financial scavengers" and extract information. In order to identify and prevent financial crime, it equips them with a variety of abilities that enable them to understand financial trends (Grubor, Ristić, & Simeunović, 2013). They employ a wide range of methods, including data mining, reporting, structured interviews with responsible parties to gather information, and a variety of quantitative tools, including vertical and horizontal ratio analysis (Akinbowale et al., 2020). The study by Kaur et al., (2022) found a positive association between forensic accounting techniques and fraud detection and control. The study by (Okoye et al. 2019) using secondary data from Nigerian brewery firms from 2010 to 2016 finds that forensic auditing positively and significantly affected the return on assets, return on equity, and EPS.

2.1.3 Concept of Forensic Accounting Techniques

Forensic accounting tools are the application and practices of knowledge and skills to help resolve criminal issues in financial misappropriation which requires legal and accounting representations. According to Eke (2019), having a solid grasp of forensic accounting procedures can help you detect criminal instances, as well as the investigative and resolution processes, so you can be a good witness when you give your report in court. The forensic accountant should have deep knowledge of law and accounting in displaying the skills and have a good representation in the court. There are four major tools that this research would be used as testable variable. They include the following:

1. The Data Mining Technique

This is a technique used by forensic accountants to detect hidden and large volume of transactions. It mines large volume of transaction through grouping. It is used for discovering, predicting and an analyzing deviation. According to Firas (2021), this technique is based on attempting to mine a huge amount of data in search of new hidden or unexpected patterns or information, and it is implemented using computer programs specifically developed for this purpose. The data mining technology assists the forensic accountant in the inquiry, but the investigation process does not end with the computer screen; it also includes document analysis, interviews, and other investigative work. In addition, the received data must be verified for accuracy and completeness.

Data mining is the process of detecting deviations, trends, and connections in massive datasets in order to anticipate outcomes. It can assist detect fraud more quickly (Bassey, 2018) by extracting, classifying, compiling, analyzing, and retrieving data. Data mining algorithms can identify trends based on accessible historical data, giving a foundation for future forecasts (Jain and Lamba, 2020). Data mining is the process of employing specialized software to identify patterns, correlations, and anomalies in databases in order to anticipate outcomes. It facilitates the extraction of hidden predictive information from large databases and can assist businesses in identifying patterns, anomalies, and other strange behaviors, enabling them to take proactive knowledge-driven decisions. Data mining software is particularly helpful in detecting fraud since it has scripting skills and can scan datasets from organizations for anomalies and suspicious patterns that are signs of fraud. This method is implemented using computer algorithms created specifically for this task, and it relies on trying to mine a sizable volume of data in search of any new hidden or unexpected patterns or information.

2. Reviewing Financial Statement

According to Tamplin (2022), financial statements are essential instruments used by companies to monitor and offer insights into the overall health and performance of their finances. These reports offer a quick overview of the cash flows, operational outcomes, and financial status of a company. Financial statements are utilized by external stakeholders including creditors, investors, analysts, and regulators in addition to being used internally by management to inform decisions. When deciding whether to lend money to a business, invest in it, or provide other types of finance, financial statements are a useful tool.

In order to check papers for validity, alteration, forgery, or counterfeiting, forensic accountants must possess specialized expertise. Therefore, by having these abilities, the forensic accountant can more easily identify mistakes, fraudulent activity, and omissions while doing his tasks, preventing and minimizing fraudulent actions (Deshi & Freeman, 2022). Zimbleman et al. (2012) stated that a forensic accountant is in charge of examining and determining the potential types of fraud as well as its signs.

3. Analyzing Accounting Records

Accounting records include all of the documents and books used in the preparation of financial statements or records for audits and financial reviews. Accounting records comprise asset and liability statements, monetary transactions, ledgers, diaries, and any supporting documents such as checks and invoices. Accounting records are frequently examined for audits, compliance checks, or other business-related requirements (Kingsley, 2020).

Kingsley (2020) said that in order to combat fraudulent activities, the forensic accountant with his skills (Technological, communications and expertise skills) in accounting knowledge can analyze accounting records and reconstruct incomplete accounting records, hence helping to detect fraud and ensuring good internal control system and good corporate governance. A forensic accountant's job entails reconstructing insufficient accounting records to settle insurance claims, overestimate inventory valuation, and prove money laundering operations by reconstructing cash transactions. Forensic accountants must be experts in financial matters and have legal knowledge to detect fraudulent acts that will be presented in a lawsuit (Kingsley, 2020).

4. Internal Control Charts.

A control chart is a graph that experts use to perform statistical process control (SPC). SPC refers to a variety of approaches and tools, including control charts, that can assist firms assess how a process evolves over time. Control charts are sometimes known as quality control charts, Shewhart charts, or process-behavior charts.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 The Fraud Management Lifecycle

Effective management of the fraud management life cycle begins with a shared awareness of the stages (Wilhelm, 2004). The fraud management lifecycle is a network lifecycle, with each stage consisting of interconnected, interdependent, and autonomous actions, functions, and operations (Albrecht et al., 2009). The fraud management lifecycle has eight stages: prevention, detection, investigation, deterrent, analysis, mitigation, policy, and prosecution (Wilhelm, 2004). Deterrence is achieved by instilling dread of the repercussions or difficulty of the perpetration in order to turn away, discourage, or prevent fraudulent action from occurring (Kimani, 2011).

Fraud investigations are focused upon three primary areas of activity; internal investigations, external investigations and law enforcement coordination. Internal investigations

include investigations of employees, contractors, consultants or vendors while external investigations are conducted on customers, fraudsters and organized groups (Wilhelm, 2004). Law enforcement coordination as further argued by Gottschalk (2010) is the provision of information and resources to, and the maintenance of, a partnership with federal, state, regional and local law enforcement authorities. Rigorous and routine investigations provide for both an incremental lift in deterrence and the maintenance of an effective relationship with law enforcement. Finally, the prosecution stage is focused upon prosecutorial and judicial authorities as well as with law enforcement (Wilhelm, 2004). The three aims of prosecution in the fraud arena are to punish the fraudster in an attempt to prevent further theft, to establish, maintain and enhance the business enterprise's reputation of deterring fraud so that the fraud community becomes aware of it and to obtain recovery or restitution wherever possible (Albrecht et al., 2009).

This theory is linked to this study. Through this theory, data mining, internal control charts and reviewing financial statements helps to support prevention, detection, investigation, and monitoring which forms part of the stages of this theory.

This study is anchored on fraud management lifecycle theory because the theory explains the rudiments and expectancies of forensic accounting techniques in detecting fraud which this study considers. The study is anchored on the fraud management lifecycle theory because the fundamental initiative in fraud management lifecycle theory is that network lifecycle where each stage in the life cycle is an aggregated entity that is made up of interrelated, interdependent and independent actions, functions and operations. This will further help in fraud detection.

2.3 Empirical Studies Review

The following are the empirical review relating to the effect of forensic accounting techniques on fraud detection by professional accounting firms in Plateau State based on the objectives of the study. They are given as follows:

1. Effect of data mining techniques on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State

Otaru and David (2023) researched on Forensic Accounting Investigation Techniques and Fraud Detection and Mitigation of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study assesses the effect of forensic accounting investigation techniques on fraud detection and mitigation of listed banks in Nigeria using three independent variables of forensic accounting interview technique, forensic accounting data mining analysis technique and forensic accounting technology technique. Survey research design was adopted by the study and it had a population of 140 respondents drawn from only operational staff of listed banks in Nigeria while the sample size of 104 was arrived at scientifically using Yaro Yamani's sample size determination technique. Data was gathered using questionnaires administered to the respondents and it was analysed using multiple regression technique. The study found that application of interview technique had positive and insignificant effect while application of data mining analysis technique and technology technique had positive and significant effect on fraud detection and mitigation of listed banks in Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended that shareholders of listed banks in Nigeria should be engaging the use of forensic accounting investigation techniques in addition to conventional annual audit because the usage of interview technique, data mining analysis technique and accounting technology technique all had positive proved to be useful tools for fraud detection and mitigation.

Hashem, Ali and Haider (2023) assessed the Impact of Forensic Accounting Techniques in Detecting Financial Fraud "Survey Study of The Opinions of Certified Accountants in Syria." The purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of forensic accounting techniques used

by certified accountants in detecting financial fraud in the companies they audit. The data was collected from primary sources based on a questionnaire distributed to (120) certified accountants who are practicing the profession for the year 2023 and are allowed to audit financial companies in Syria. The results showed a statistically significant impact of the forensic accounting techniques (financial ratio analysis - trend analysis - data mining - critical point audit - relative size theory) used by the certified accountant in detecting financial fraud in Syria. It showed a positive and statistically significant effect of the forensic accounting techniques used by the certified accountant in detecting financial fraud in Syria after controlling years of experience.

Ibrahim (2022) researched on Investigation Techniques, Methods, Types, and Increasing Impact of Forensic Accounting in Digital Period. The aim was to look at how Forensic accountants are responsible for fighting financial malpractices and fraud in organizations and businesses. Financial accounting applications are made successful through engagement in duties such as financial data mining analysis, preparation of reports, and testing the results before courts. Investigation involves examination of record books to determine if a financial criminal activity has occurred. Through these investigations, forensic accountants find and discover fraud and malpractices thus bringing the culprits to books. The reports filed act as evidence in courts. Forensic accounting has played an important role in fighting fraud, solving civil disputes, and helped companies avoid future crimes regarding finances.

Akuchi and Onyema (2020) examined forensic accounting techniques used to detect labor fraud in the state of Anambra, Nigeria. The result of the study suggests that there are no generally accepted forensic investigation techniques to detect fraud in the public sector and that there is a positive and significant association between forensic accounting methods and fraud detection in the public sector. The research found that data mining techniques should be fully applied in public sector fraud detection in Nigeria.

Another study by Mbasiti, Gyang and Ojaide (2021) examined the extent to which forensic accounting techniques serve as a panacea for preventing revenue leakages in federal universities in Nigeria. The study revealed that forensic the use of data analysis tools has a positive impact on income leakages in Nigerian federal institutions. The study advised that forensic accounting data analysis techniques be used at Nigerian federal universities to help reduce income leakages in the system and that relevant authorities assist in ensuring that this is done. Also, forensic accounting technologies should be deployed and applied to prevent revenue leakages.

Ezenwafor and Udukeke (2019) examined the utilisation of data mining and anonymous communication techniques for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State due to the growing incidence of frauds that are crippling businesses and socio-economic development of the state. The results showed that the accounting staff lowly utilised data mining and anonymous techniques for fraud detection. Furthermore, it was found that the types and status of organization in NSE significantly influenced respondents' ratings on the utilization of data mining but did not influence their ratings on the utilisation of anonymous communications for fraud detection. From the findings of the study, it was concluded that the accounting staff did not utilize forensic auditing investigation techniques for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations as required. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended among others, that shareholders and directors of large-scale business organisations should provide regular training on data mining techniques to equip their accounting staff with the relevant and up-to-date skills, abilities, attitudes, and competencies for fraud detection.

2. The effect of reviewing financial statement on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State

Deshi and Freeman (2022) examined the impact of forensic accounting on financial fraud detection and prevention in deposit money banks in Nigeria. Primary source of data was adopted Data were collected from internal control, audit and compliance staff from the eight (8) deposit money banks license with international authorization operating in Nigerian banking sector through well-structured Likert scale questionnaire. 120 questionnaires were issued to respondents from eight banks. The statistical tool used in the analysis of the data collected was Descriptive Statistics and multiple regression analysis. The data were processed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study found that there is a positive relationship between Forensic Accounting Investigation, and fraud detection, also, Reviewing Financial Transactions and Analyzing Accounting Records have a positive impact on fraud detection. The study concluded from the findings that conducting forensic accounting investigation has a positive and significant effect on financial fraud detection in DMBs in Nigeria. On the other hand, analyzing financial transactions has a negative or no significant effect on financial fraud detection in DMBs operations. However, it was concluded that analyzing financial records positively and significantly influences fraud detection money deposit banks in Nigeria. The study recommended that, Forensic Accountants' services should be maintained in the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks as independent concern in order to mitigate fraudulent financial transactions.

Aminian and Tahriri (2021) assessed in a paper titled creating an interpretative structural model of the factors affecting the quality of forensic accounting in Iran. The study found that the goals and missions of forensic accounting, forensic accounting standards and reviews, professional skills, academic training, enactment of forensic accounting, and the need for a forensic accountant in organisations improve the quality of forensic accounting. The study recommended that a specialised institution related to forensic accounting be established in Iran and, based on the model presented in this research, implement the quality framework of forensic accounting in Iran in a desirable manner and also that a wide range of experts be used in future research to find factors affecting the quality of forensic accounting.

Ojukwu, et al. (2020) also conducted a study titled on Forensic Accounting and Fraud Detection in Nigerian Universities (A Study of Cross River University of Technology). This study discovered a substantial association between forensic accounting and financial fraud detection, as well as a large relationship between forensic accounting and financial reporting quality. There was also a significant relationship between forensic accounting and internal control. The study concluded that forensic accounting services provide tertiary institutions with the necessary tools to deter fraudulent activities but do not curb fraudulent activities and recommended that the eradication of economic and financial crime through the incorporation of forensic accounting into the system will enhance the image of the universities under consideration.

Okoye and Ndah (2019) examined the connection between forensic litigation support techniques and fraud detection in Nigerian manufacturing firms. Data was gathered from primary sources by sending fifty (50) standardized questionnaires to ten (10) accounting departments of the selected manufacturing firms. Multiple regression tests were performed on the collected data using the Ordinary Least Square method. The study's results revealed that fraud investigation activities and fraud prevention in manufacturing firms have a favorable and statistically relevant relationship. The results also revealed that fraud litigation activities and fraud prevention in manufacturing companies have a favorable and statistically relevant relationship.

3. The effect of analyzing accounting records technique on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State

Dada and Audu (2021) examined relevance of forensic accounting in the prevention and detection of tax frauds in federally collected taxes in Nigeria. The survey research design approach was adopted for the study. Data was obtained via a structured questionnaire administered to a population made up of staff members of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the four main professional accounting firms reputable for rendering forensic accounting investigation services in Nigeria. A sample size of 254 out of 394 respondents was selected using the purposive sampling technique. The study found that forensic accounting of analyzing accounting records had a significant and positive effect on prevention and detection of tax frauds. The study recommended that the training routine of the FIRS staffs be further fortified so as to scale up their proficiency in forensic accounting while the government should consider setting up of witness protection schemes to further increase the confidence of expert witnesses and guarantee their safety.

Edward (2021) focused on impact of forensic accounting on financial fraud detection in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The forensic accounting as independent variable proxied by conducting investigation, analyzing financial transaction and reconstructing incomplete accounting records while financial fraud detection as dependent variable. The survey research design and primary data sources were adopted. The structured five (5) point likert scale close ended questionnaire was used for the study. The SPSS version 20 was used to analyze both descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The findings indicate that conducting investigation, analyzing financial transaction and reconstructing incomplete accounting

Hashem (2020) investigated the role of forensic accounting approaches in detecting non-numerical fraud risk variables in Amman Stock Exchange manufacturing businesses. The study recommended enhancing awareness of applying forensic accounting techniques' importance among chartered accountants. And, motivating them to use the forensic accounting techniques to detect any fraud practice and concluded that all independent variables of forensics have a high role in detecting fraud risk factors.

Eze and Okoye (2019) studied the effects of forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in Imo State's public sector in Nigeria. The study provided a correlation between forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the public sector and advised that forensic accounting be strengthened in the public sector and that the top-level management should be committed to the program while the anti-graft agencies like the EFCC and ICPC should be repositioned to adopt forensic accounting techniques and also concluded that forensic accounting is important in the public sector given the huge amount of public fund that is rampantly embezzled or swindled.

Joseph, Okike and Yoko (2016) investigated the extent to which forensic accounting contribute to the detection of fraud in Nigeria. By employing survey research, which involves the collection of primary data with the aid of questionnaire administered to 92 sampled professional accountants in Nigerian public sector, and by analyzing data gathered via the statistical method of chi-square, findings from the study suggest that forensic accounting have a significant role to play in fraud detection and prevention in Nigeria. However, this study suffers from the use of non-parametric statistical technique, whose results cannot be meaningfully generalized.

4. Internal Control Charts and fraud Detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State

Ojo-Agboju et al. (2022) examined how forensic accounting influenced fraud detection and prevention in a few Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Using their survey design, Access Bank, First Bank, GT Bank, Union Bank, UBA, and Zenith Bank recruited 115 resident internal control officials, branch operation managers, and cash officers/head tellers as a sample for the study. The questionnaire was given to the participants using a straightforward, proportionate random sample approach. Their investigation, which employed basic linear regression, revealed a strong correlation between forensic accounting and fraud detection even if it had no effect on fraud prevention in the DMBs they mentioned. The investigation came to the conclusion that fraud in the DMB branch operations in Nigeria could not be stopped by forensic accounting.

Ismail, (2020) examined forensic accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the Nigerian public sector. This paper was aimed at empirically evaluating the relationship between forensic Accounting and fraud detection and prevention in the Nigerian public sector. The study used a survey design utilizing a sample size of one fifty (50) respondents which consist of auditors and accountants in ten (10) ministries selected from FCT Abuja in Nigeria. Analysis of variance, (ANOVA) used to test the hypotheses at 5% significant level. Findings of the study revealed that the use of forensic accounting in the Nigerian public sector is effective in detecting fraud; there is also a significant correlation between forensic accounting and the litigation support service in Nigerian courts. Similarly, use of forensic accounting in the public sector is also effective in preventing fraud. The study recommended that the public sector should install an uninterrupted enhancement in the internal control system and introduce effective and efficient internal check and monitoring, they should adopt an effective accounting system capable of holding officers accountable for their actions. Forensic accountant should be made to undergo appropriate training on forensic accounting skills.

Lawal, et al. (2020) examined the effect of forensic accounting on fraud detection in the manufacturing industry in Nigeria. The study employed the survey design and data were collected using primary data and this was achieved via a structured questionnaire. The population of the study consists of all the employees of PZ Nigeria Limited. Regression analysis was used to show the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable. The study found that there is a significant effect of forensic accounting on fraud detection.

The effect of forensic accounting on the detection and prevention of fraud in the Nigeria banking industry was investigated by Oyebisi et al (2018). The study used a survey research design, with primary data as the source. The data was gathered from survey questions distributed to sample organizations. Three (3) hypotheses were developed and tested using Simple regression, Independent Test, and one-way ANOVA at a significance level of 5%. The findings showed a negative significant relationship between the implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and foreign direct investment in Nigerian banks. According to the findings, forensic litigation support has a significant impact on fraud detection. Furthermore, the results of this study showed that the Nigerian banking industry has a poor knowledge of forensic litigation support. As a result, the study suggested that the Government of Nigeria create an enabling atmosphere for the forensic litigation support profession to prosper by improving the overall regulatory, professional, and political frameworks.

3.0 Methodology

A survey design was adopted for the study. Its anonymity necessitated by the sensitive nature of the subject of this study allowed participants to make honest responses. The survey design was an appropriate choice for this study because the researcher hopes to examine the predictive relationship between the independent variables (Forensic Accounting Techniques) and the dependent variable (Fraud Detection)

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

In this study the population of the study consisted of 203 staff from the selected Professional accounting firms in Jos Plateau State. The total populations constitute of 203 staff (Auditors and Accountants) from the six (6) Professional accounting firms chosen to determine the sample size for this study. Table 1 below shows the professional accounting firms used to determine the total number of staff.

Table 3.1: Professional Accounting firms

S/N	Professional Accounting Firms	Number of Staff
1.	Ekoja B.Ekoja & Co.	19
2.	Moses Adeboye & Co.	24
3.	G.B Ojo & Co.	45
4.	Razak Adeniyi Ayilara & Co	31
5	William Adjekughele & Co.	39
6.	Micheal Akano & Co.	45
	TOTAL	203

Source: www.businesslist.com.ng, 2024

The statistical formula applied to determine the sample size of the study is;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population

1 = Constant

e = Sample error (Usually 0.10, 0.05, and 0.01 acceptable error)

(Taro Yamani)

$$n = \frac{203}{1 + 203(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{203}{1 + 0.5075}$$

$$n = \frac{203}{1.5075}$$

$$n = 134.66$$

It is on the sample size of 135 that questionnaire distribution was based using convenient sampling techniques to the firms that make up my sample populations.

The study employed the use of primary data using structured questionnaire. The study used a structured questionnaire, which comprised of close-ended questions to understand the

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effects of forensic accounting tools in fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. Sutherland’s approach measuring scale was used for this research work. The scale was introduced by Dame Joan Sutherland (1939) which was used to influence the white-collar crime theory adopted for this work.

This study examined the effect of Forensic Accounting Tools on Fraud Detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Nigeria. The study variables consist of Fraud Detection (FFD) as the dependent variable, data mining techniques (DMT), Reviewing Financial Statement Techniques (RFST), Analyzing Accounting Records Techniques (AART) and Internal Control Charts (ICC) as the independent proxies. The study was analysed using multiple regression technique of data analysis through the aid SPSS Version 26 because it shows the strength of relationship between dependent and independent variables.

The model for this study thus is stated in its functional form below:

$$FD = f(DMT, RFST, ACRT, ICC)$$

However, in order to take into account the deterministic and stochastic aspects of the model it is therefore stated in an econometric form:

$$FD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DMT + \beta_2 RFST + \beta_3 ACRT + \beta_4 ICC + \mu$$

Where:

FD= Fraud detection as dependable variable

DMT = Data Mining techniques

RFST = Reviewing Financial Statement Techniques

ACRT= Analyzing Accounting Records Techniques

ICCA= Internal Control Charts

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the coefficients

β_0 = Constant

μ = error term for the Model that is, the difference between the observed value and the predicted value of fraud reduction.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive analysis is seen basically from the behavior of the descriptive statistics and the correlations. The above parameters are necessary to check if the statistical mean of the data provides a good fit of the observed data (descriptive statistics). The descriptive analysis is seen basically from the behavior of the descriptive statistics and the correlations of the observed data (descriptive statistics) and whether the study variables have effects. Data collected using the questionnaires are presented, analyzed and discussed in a summarized format.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the study variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Fraud Detection	129	1.14	4.29	2.1717	.68521
Data Mining Technique	129	1.00	3.40	1.9194	.60752
Reviewing Financial Statement technique	129	1.00	4.40	2.3938	.93305
Analyzing accounting Record Technique	129	1.00	4.00	2.3938	.98328
Internal control chart	129	1.00	3.80	2.4388	.87610

Source: SPSS Output v.26

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Fraud detection has a mean of 2.1717, a standard deviation of 0.68521, a minimum of 1.14 and a maximum of 4.29, indicating that fraud detection in professional accounting firms is highly dispersed because the mean is far from the standard deviation. Data mining technique (DMT) has a mean of 1.9194 with a standard deviation of 0.60752, minimum and maximum values of 1.00 and 3.40 respectively suggesting a wide dispersion. The mean of Reviewing Financial Statement technique is 2.3938, with a standard deviation of 0.93305 and a minimum and maximum values of 1 and 4.40, respectively. The result shows that most of the respondents agreed that forensic accounting techniques have effect on fraud detection in accounting professional accounting. Also Analyzing accounting Record Technique had a mean and standard deviation values of 2.3938 and 0.98328 respectively and maintaining the same minimum with Reviewing Financial Statement technique but with the maximum of 4.00, implying that accounting records can be analyse through different methods depending on the kind of fraud needed to be unveiled. Lastly, internal control charts show that there is wide dispersion with the mean of 2.4388 and standard deviation of 0.87610, having minimum and maximum of 1.00 and 3.80 respectively.

The descriptive statistics for the study variables are presented in Table 1 indicate that the mean score of the latent variables range between 1.92 and 2.44 on a 5- point Likert scale, while the standard deviation ranges between 0.61 and 0.98. The standard deviations are small relative to their respective means, implying that the statistical mean provides a good fit of the observed data (Field, 2009).

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Multiple regression analysis was then employed to test the effect of the predictors on the criterion variable and hypotheses earlier formulated in the study. A multiple regression was run to test the effect. Table 10 presents the results.

Table 2: Table of Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.298	.214		6.064	.000
	Data Mining Technique	.153	.083	.136	1.854	.006
	Reviewing Financial Statement technique	-.268	.058	-.366	-4.642	.000
	Analyzing accounting Record Technique	.045	.064	.065	.711	.479
	Internal control chart	.456	.071	.584	6.449	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Fraud Detection

Decision Rule

If the sig. value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. Conversely, if the sig. value is greater than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis One

The hypothesis one is restated as follows:

H0₁: Data mining technique has no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. From the regression analysis run, given the coefficients in table 2 above, it shows that data mining technique has positive and insignificant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, given ($\beta = 0.136$, $t = 1.854$; sig.

0.006). Thus, data mining technique has positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State

Test of Hypothesis Two

The hypothesis two is restated as follows:

H0₂: Reviewing financial statement techniques has no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional Accounting Firms in Plateau State. The regression analysis run, given the coefficients in table 2 above, shows that reviewing financial statement techniques has negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, given ($\beta = -0.366$, $t = -4.642$; sig. 0.000). Thus, reviewing financial statement techniques has negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State.

Test of Hypothesis Three

The hypothesis three is restated as follows:

H0₃: Analyzing accounting records techniques have no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. The regression analysis run, given the coefficients in table 2 above, shows that analyzing accounting records techniques have positive and insignificant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, given ($\beta = 0.065$, $t = 0.711$; sig. 0.479). Thus, analyzing accounting records techniques have positive and not significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State.

Test of Hypothesis Four

The hypothesis four is restated as follows:

H0₄: Internal control charts have no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. From the regression analysis run, given the coefficients in table 2 above, it shows that Internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, given ($\beta = 0.584$, $t = 6.449$; sig. 0.000). Thus, internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State.

4.3 Summary and Discussion of Findings

The study carried out the t-test to each beta coefficient in the fitted regression models. This indicates that Forensic Accounting Investigation positively and significantly influences Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, given $\beta = 0.136$, $t = 1.854$ and p-value of $0.006 < 0.05$. It implies that for every unit increase in the forensic accounting investigation there is an increase in fraud detection by 0.136 units. This finding aligns with the study of Otaru and David (2023) who discovered that data mining analysis technique and technology technique had positive and significant effect on fraud detection and mitigation of listed banks in Nigeria. This finding is also in line with that of Mbasiti et al., (2021) who found that accounting data analysis technique had positive effect on prevention of revenue leakage in Nigerian public universities. It is also in line with the studies of Ibrahim (2022), Ewa (2022) and Ogiriki and Appah (2018) who found out that all the measurements of forensic accounting and auditing techniques including data mining technique have positive significant effect on fraud in Nigeria. This finding opposes that of Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) who found that the usage of forensic accounting services was not effective in the determination of fraudulent cases among listed firms.

Also, it indicates that reviewing financial statement has negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State with $\beta = -0.366$, $t = -4.642$; sig. $0.000 < 0.05$. It implies that for every unit increase in reviewing financial transactions there is a decrease in fraud detection by 0.366 units. This finding is in line with the findings of Deshi and Freeman (2022) who found out that Reviewing Financial Transactions has a significant impact on fraud detection. It also aligns with the studies of Aminian and Tahriri (2021), Ojukwu, et al.

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(2020), Okoye and Ndah (2019). This finding contradicts the study of Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) who found that the usage of forensic accounting services was not effective in the determination of fraudulent cases among listed firms.

Furthermore, the study carried out the t-test to each beta coefficient in the fitted regression models. It discovered that analyzing accounting records techniques have no significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State given $\beta=0.065$, $t=0.711$; P-value of $0.479 > 0.05$. It implies that for every unit increase in analyzing financial records there is an increase in fraud detection by 0.065 units. The study reveals that analyzing accounting records has a positive and significant effect on detecting financial fraud in DMBs. Therefore, it can be said that with detail analysis of financial books by forensic accountant can unveil hidden fraudulent activities. This finding corroborates with the study of Deshi and Freeman (2022) who found out that analyzing accounting record has a positive impact on fraud detection. It is in agreement with the study of Edward (2021) whose findings indicate that conducting investigation, analyzing financial transaction and reconstructing incomplete accounting records have significant effect on financial fraud detection in deposit money banks in Nigeria. This finding also aligns with the findings of Hashem (2020) who found out that analyzing accounting records technique helps in detecting non-numerical fraud risk variables in Amman Stock Exchange manufacturing businesses. This finding opposes the study of Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) who found that the usage of forensic accounting services was not effective in the determination of fraudulent cases among listed firms.

Lastly, from the regression analysis run above. Internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State with $\beta=0.584$, $t=6.449$; sig. $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, Internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. The study findings agree with the study of Bangura (2020) who conducted a similar study in Sierra Leone and found out forensic accounting techniques have a positive significant effect on internal control chart. This finding is not in agreement with the study of Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) who found that the usage of forensic accounting services was not effective in the determination of fraudulent cases among listed firms.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on findings, the study concludes as follows; Firstly, the study has provided both empirical and statistical evidence on the utility of four independent variables that constitute; data mining techniques, reviewing financial statement, analyzing accounting records technique and internal control charts in determining Fraud Detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State, Nigeria. The study concludes that that forensic accounting data mining technique had a positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. This therefore provides evidence that data mining technique has a significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. Also, the study also concludes that forensic accounting reviewing financial statement technique had a negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. This therefore provides evidence that the greater the reviewing financial statement technique, the higher the chance to detect fraud by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. Furthermore, the study concludes that analyzing accounting records techniques have positive and insignificant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. Similarly, the study found that Internal control charts have positive and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State. The overall conclusion of the study is that accounting data mining technique and Internal control charts had a positive and significant on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State forensic accounting reviewing

financial statement technique had a negative and significant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State while Forensic Accounting Techniques has significant effect of on Fraud Detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State while analyzing accounting records techniques have positive and insignificant effect on fraud detection by Professional accounting firms in Plateau State.

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Professional accounting firms and other private organizations should select data mining software that integrates with existing accounting systems. This would require that relevant data and software be chosen, extracted and integrated for efficient detection of fraud.
2. Professional accounting firms should maintain the services of forensic accountants to review their financial statements and transactions at the end of the period of transactions. This will help to verify the effectiveness of financial reporting controls over time.
3. Professional accounting firms should employ the services of forensic accountants to help them unveil fraudulent records from their financial books. This firms should document procedures for future reference and stay updated on changing accounting standards and regulations.
4. Professional accounting firms should determine critical internal controls for financial reporting, and also to refine charts based on changing risks and controls.

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